

Hydrogen internal combustion engine CHP in decentralized energy systems: Towards TEA-LCA in an open-source framework

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KEYWORDS

Environmental Impact, Life Cycle Assessment, Hydrogen, Energy systems, Techno Economic Analysis, Cogeneration, Combined Heat and Power

HIGHLIGHTS

- Towards OpenModelica-TEA and Brightway2-LCA integration for H₂-ICE-CHP systems
- Real hourly demand data of Offenburg (Germany) municipality buildings used
- PV overproduction and system boundaries strongly shape environmental assessment
- H₂ sub-system shows low GHG but relevant burdens in other environmental categories
- Open-source workflow for transparency in local energy policy planning

ABSTRACT

Hydrogen-based decentralized energy systems (H₂-DES) are gaining prominence as potential solutions for local decarbonization of heat and power supply. This paper presents a life cycle assessment (LCA) of a H₂-DES using an internal combustion engine for combined heat and power (ICE-CHP), grounded on a techno-economic analysis (TEA) model implemented in OpenModelica. The study addresses the relative underexploration of H₂-ICE-CHP technologies in the LCA literature, offering a comprehensive analysis based on real hourly demand data of buildings in Offenburg (Germany), a municipality involved in the Franco-German Interreg CO2InnO project. Scenarios families were developed with varying configurations and dimensioning (PV, wind, battery, H₂ storage). The results of the TEA model were interfaced with the Brightway2 framework for LCA through custom Python-based routines and manual implementation. Monte Carlo simulations and global sensitivity analysis were conducted in the Activity-Browser software to evaluate uncertainty and parameter influence. Results show that impacts are strongly dependent of the scenario family and the system boundaries. The H₂ sub-system components showed modest impacts to climate change but not in other environmental categories, while PV significantly affected environmental assessment overall, depending on excess electricity consideration. These findings highlight the necessity of careful system design and boundary comparison in policy and environmental reporting. This work also contributes methodologically towards the development of an open-source TEA-LCA workflow. While still requiring manual data adaptations, it forms the foundation for future automation efforts. The approach offers actionable insights for local policymakers and researchers aiming for transparent, reproducible, and multi-criteria sustainability assessments of H₂-DES.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen has attracted growing attention in recent years, both for its current industrial uses – which require decarbonization – and its potential role in decarbonizing heavy transport, heating networks, and inter-seasonal electricity storage (Sadeq et al., 2024). Strategic divergences exist within the European Union (EU), notably between France and Germany. France, with its already low-carbon electricity mix, prioritizes decarbonizing hydrogen used in industry and agriculture. In contrast, Germany’s diverse industrial interests promote a broader range of hydrogen applications (Quitow & Zabanova, 2024). At the EU level, efforts to establish a pan-European hydrogen market have led to initiatives such as the European Hydrogen Backbone (EHB, 2025), which brings together gas operators pursuing energy transition. Within this context, the Interreg CO2InnO project serves as a Franco-German cross-border living laboratory aimed at comprehensively assessing decentralized energy systems (DES) using hydrogen (H₂), particularly for heat decarbonization (CO2InnO, 2025). It explores H₂ use in high-efficiency combined heat and power (CHP) plants, for which several alternative technologies are available (Yu et al., 2023). In particular, one of the objectives of the CO2InnO project is to develop tools for stakeholders (e.g., local authorities, NGOs, companies) to test various DES configurations and assess their technical feasibility, economic viability, and environmental impact.

Numerous environmental studies have examined H₂-based DES, employing diverse scopes, applications, and methodologies (Yue et al., 2021; Eriksson & Gray, 2017; Valente, 2017; Zhang et al., 2025; Le et al., 2024a, 2024b; Sharma et al., 2023; Song et al., 2023; Sharma et al., 2020). While H₂ use is often considered climate-neutral at the usage stage, life cycle assessments (LCA) enable to reveal the whole picture of environmental impacts throughout the life cycle and don’t limit the assessment to CO₂ emissions, also taking into account abiotic resources and water consumption, human and ecological toxicity, etc (Zhao et al., 2020; Gerloff et al., 2021). Most LCA studies focus on fuel cells (FCs)-based DES due to their high efficiency and relative novelty (Chadly et al., 2022; Gandiglio et al., 2022; Peppas et al., 2021; Rossi et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2017; Ren et al., 2016), typically evaluating impact reductions relative to fossil-fuel-based systems (Bionaz et al., 2022; Gandiglio et al., 2022). In contrast, H₂-based DES using internal combustion engines (ICE) remain underexplored, despite advantages such as greater contamination tolerance, technological maturity, and lower reliance on scarce materials (Stępień et al., 2021).

Moreover, there is a growing trend towards integration of techno-economic analysis (TEA) with life cycle assessment (LCA). While LCA is the most comprehensive method for environmental assessment, it typically focuses on technology comparison using standardized functional units (e.g., “1 kWh of electricity produced”). TEA, often grounded in process and flow simulations, complements LCA by enabling more context-specific and operationally relevant assessments. Their combination is seen as a path toward more transparent, localized, and multi-criteria evaluations (Ferdous et al., 2023). However, integrated TEA-LCA approaches face methodological challenges, including limited access to technical, economic, and territorial data, as well as a lack of integrated operational tools (Ribon, 2020; Mahmud et al., 2021). Notably, recent integrated TEA-LCA propositions for H₂-based DES rely on proprietary software (Sharma et al., 2023; Le et al., 2024), potentially hindering both research progress and accessibility for resource-constrained users.

The present work thus aims to conduct a TEA-grounded LCA of a H₂-ICE-CHP based DES to fill a gap in the contemporary literature, and contribute to the development of open-source approaches for combined TEA-LCA. It is built on a case study of the Offenburg municipality (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany), which provided real data regarding several buildings energy requirements, with hourly resolution over a year. This municipality is a partner of the CO2InnO project, representative of small to medium cities wishing to decarbonize their electricity and mostly their heat demand, but which will not be connected to the future hydrogen backbone before 2035 at least. A simulated energy system has been developed in OpenModelica (Fritzson et al., 2020) following a TEA approach (Beerlage et al. 2024). Based on the different outlined scenarios, we conduct a comparative LCA taking into account the multiple possible pathways of energy and mass throughout the different system components, using dedicated Python procedures for flows’ reconstruction and the Brightway2 open-source framework for LCA, which is also Python-based (Mutel, 2018).

2. GOAL AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

2.1. OBJECTIVE & METHODOLOGY

The simulated energy system developed in OpenModelica (Fritzon et al., 2020) using a TEA framework (Beerlage et al., 2024) was used to generate several quantitative scenarios with hourly resolution of flows over a year. Based on the results outlined, a comparative cradle-to-grave LCA (compliant with ISO 14040/44) was conducted to evaluate the environmental impacts of the DES configurations identified in the TEA study. Mass and energy balances for each scenario were reconstructed from OpenModelica outputs using custom Python procedures within Jupyter Notebooks – see **Appendix**. The LCA was implemented using the Brightway2 open-source framework (Mutel, 2018) via the Activity Browser GUI (Steubing et al., 2020). The background system was modeled using the ecoinvent 3.10 database with the “allocation, cut-off by classification” approach. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) was initially performed using the EU-recommended EF v3.1 method, which includes 16 environmental indicators (Andreasi Bassi et al., 2023). For clarity and relevance, five key indicators were selected for detailed analysis – **Table 1**. Uncertainty analysis was conducted through Monte Carlo simulations, followed by global sensitivity analysis (GSA) to identify key contributors to result variability.

Table 1. Environmental indicators used to assess the decentralized ‘stand-alone’ energy system based on H₂ ICE-CHP.

Environmental category	Impact indicator
Climate change	Global Warming Potential (GWP100)
Ecotoxicity (freshwater)	USEtox / Ecotoxicity: freshwater (ECOTOX-FW)
Human toxicity (carcinogenic)	USEtox / Human toxicity: carcinogenic (HT-C)
Resource consumption	Abiotic Depletion Potential: ultimate reserves (ADP-UR)
Water use	User Deprivation Potential (UDP-WU)

2.2. FUNCTIONAL UNIT

The functional unit, defined as the "quantified performance of a product system used as a reference unit in life cycle assessment," is set as "one year of operation of the H₂ ICE-CHP-based DES, calibrated to meet heat demand." This definition reflects that the system’s decentralized character is primarily related to heat supply, while electricity exchange with the grid remains readily achievable. The annual heat and electricity demand respectively amounted to 1,410 MJ and 297.3 MWh.

2.3. SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

The investigated system, illustrated in **Figure 1**, consists of three interconnected subsystems: electrical, thermal, and hydrogen. As the central element, the heating system was dimensioned based on economic optimization.

Several scenarios were designed to assess how variations in hydrogen storage (H₂S) capacity affect the feasibility and efficiency of the H₂ ICE-CHP-based DES (Beerlage et al., 2024). H₂S was selected as a key variable due to its practical and economic constraints, including large volume requirements and high capital costs, which present major barriers in real-world implementation. By varying storage volumes, the study sought to identify an optimal size that balances hydrogen production and consumption without increasing emissions or inefficiencies. Given the system’s heat-oriented design, the primary goal was to meet thermal demand; electricity production via photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbines (WT) was primarily intended to support hydrogen generation rather than grid supply. This focus on heat demand influenced both control strategies and the sizing of key components such as the CHP unit and hydrogen storage. Scenario variables are detailed in **Table 2**.

139
140

141 **Figure 1.** Overview of the decentralized ‘stand-alone’ energy system based on H₂ ICE-CHP. Adapted from
142 (Beerlage et al. 2024).

143

144 **Table 2.** Overview of the scenarios specifications for the decentralized ‘stand-alone’ energy system based on H₂
145 ICE-CHP.

Scenario	ICE-CHP _{el} (kW)	ICE-CHP _{th} (kW)	PV (MWp)	WT (MWp)	BAT (kWh)	GSHP (kW)	TES (m ³)	PEMEL (MW)	H2S (m ³)
PV + WT + BAT			0,9	0,5					
WT + BAT	38	53,7	0	0,5	500	197	5	0,5	1000, 500,
PV + BAT			1,8	0					100, 50,
PV					0				30, 10, 1

146

147 Given the system’s ability to exchange electricity with the grid, multiple system boundaries can be defined for
148 impact assessment, each yielding distinct results and interpretations. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, three
149 boundary scenarios were considered. In the ‘Load’ (L) boundary, only the flows directly meeting the heat and
150 electricity demands of the Offenburg buildings are included. The ‘Load + Excess’ (LE) boundary also accounts
151 for the environmental burden of the electricity overproduction which is not consumed by the buildings. Lastly, the
152 ‘Load + Excess - Grid(DE)’ (LEG) boundary consequently assumes that the excess electricity is exported to the
153 GRID for other uses. It replaces an equivalent amount of electricity from the German electricity mix, thereby
154 potentially crediting the system with avoided emissions.

3. INVENTORY ANALYSIS

3.1. DATA ORIGIN AND UNCERTAINTIES

As part of the CO2InnO project, the city of Offenburg (Germany) provided hourly heat and electricity demand data over one year for five buildings. These buildings were modeled as a single system with shared infrastructure, based on simplifying assumptions agreed upon by project partners. Weather inputs were sourced from the open-source CBA Clima tool (Betti et al., 2024), using data from nearby Strasbourg (France) due to the absence of a dedicated Offenburg dataset. Mass and energy flows derived from simulations depend on quality of the OpenModelica model. Since the system design centers on a ICE-CHP unit and a proton-exchange membrane electrolyzer (PEMEL), these components' models were validated in the original TEA study (Beerlage et al., 2024). The average relative deviation was ~10% between model and lab measurements for the PEMEL, and 1-4% compared to manufacturer specifications or the Hofner model for the ICE-CHP unit.

Uncertainty analysis incorporated the existing uncertainty data from the ecoinvent v3.10 database for the background system. As most ecoinvent processes required scaling to align with the TEA-modeled system components, additional uncertainties were introduced using triangular distributions and pedigree matrix-based methods for modified flows – **Sections 3.3-3.6**. Monte Carlo simulations were performed with 1,000 iterations for each scenario. It is important to note that the Activity Browser does not include uncertainty data for characterization factors (CFs); thus, uncertainty propagation in the results reflects only the background and adapted foreground systems.

3.2. MASS/ENERGY FLOWS RECONSTRUCTION

The OpenModelica model generates hourly outputs for a representative year, detailing electricity, heat, hydrogen production and consumption among other variables. However, due to the model's mathematical structure, it does not directly provide component-level input and output flows, which are required for LCA calculations. To address this, a Python script embedded in a Jupyter Notebook was developed to extract, process, and validate the data, enabling reconstruction of the necessary flows – see **Appendix**. The TEA model outputs incorporates the system's control logic (Beerlage et al., 2024). Thus, flow attribution can be performed on each hourly output of the model using a simple proportionality method as described in **Eq. 1**:

$$flow(Source \rightarrow Sink) = \frac{Source}{Supply} \cdot \frac{Sink}{Demand} \cdot \min(Supply, Demand) \quad (Eq.1)$$

With:

- *Source*: starting point of the given flow
- *Sink*: ending point of the given flow
- *Supply*: sum of all source productions of the given flow
- *Demand*: sum of all sink consumptions of the given flow

The reconstructed flows, integrated over the year, are displayed as Sankey diagrams in **Figure 2**. As the system is primarily dimensioned to continuously meet heat demand, scenarios including PV exhibit substantial electricity overproduction, with 99.3–99.8% of PV-generated electricity exported to the grid (“PV→GRID” flow). Similar trends are observed for other electricity sources: 52.6–67.1% of WT electricity and 36.9–42.1% of ICE-CHP electricity is also surplus. H₂S has limited effect on electricity overproduction, except in the 1 m³ case, where ICE-CHP overproduction increases to 74%. In contrast, scenarios without PV show significantly reduced overproduction, ranging from 0.8–24.4% for WT and 0.4–9.7% for ICE-CHP. In all cases, electricity overproduction increases as H₂S decreases. Direct H₂ use in the ICE-CHP without intermediate storage follows the same inverse relationship with H₂S, with values ranging from 27.9–48.0% in scenarios comprising PV and 14.8–65.5% in non-PV scenarios. These reconstructed mass and energy balances enable detailed LCA modeling of the system's operational phase for each scenario. They also incorporate the efficiency assumptions from the TEA model in OpenModelica. Accordingly, the generic operational data in the ecoinvent datasets used for the

204 LCA (see Sections 3.3 to 3.6) were replaced when necessary to ensure consistency with the system behavior as
 205 modeled in the TEA approach.
 206

207
 208 **Figure 2.** Overview of the flows balance in the energy system for the different families of scenarios, based on the
 209 case of H2S = 50 m³. Flows' widths are scaled per flow type to make proportions inside a type of flow more
 210 readable.
 211

212 3.3. INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE CHP

213
 214 This central component was modeled using the “*heat and power co-generation unit, X kW electrical, lean burn*
 215 (*CH*)” activities from the ecoinvent database, with X values of 50, 200, 500, and 1,000 kW_{el}. These datasets are
 216 extrapolations from an empirical dataset corresponding to a real 160 kW_{el} ICE-CHP unit fueled by natural gas
 217 (Heck, 2007). The “lean burn” configuration was selected to avoid the inclusion of a catalytic converter, which is
 218 absent from the referenced datasets. The associated infrastructure datasets – for “*common components*” and for
 219 “*electricity/heat only*” components – share identical flow structures across capacities, enabling us to apply a
 220 scaling approach following Zhang et al. (2017), as formalized in Eq. 2:
 221

$$222 \quad \frac{c_2}{c_1} = \left(\frac{x_2}{x_1}\right)^b \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

223
 224 With:

- 225 • C₁: known flow of component 1
- 226 • C₂: unknown flow of component 2
- 227 • X₁: capacity (here, kW) of system 1
- 228 • X₂: capacity (here, kW) of system 2
- 229 • b: scaling factor

230
 231 Having multiple reference datasets enabled separate fitting of each flow's evolution to determine the extrapolation
 232 method used in constructing these datasets. Using Eq. 3, all coefficients of determination (R²) exceeded 0.999,
 233 indicating an excellent fit:
 234

$$235 \quad C(X) = a \cdot X^b \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

236
 237

238 Where:

- 239 • C : flow value
- 240 • a : regression coefficient across the datasets (not just the ratio of 2 X values)
- 241 • X : capacity (here, kW)
- 242 • b : scaling factor

243

244 The determined a and b values were used to derive the flow values for the infrastructure dataset of our 38 kW_{el}
245 (+53.7 kW_{th}) ICE-CHP, allowing consistency with the existing datasets. The "storage production, 10,000 l"
246 ecoinvent activity of the original datasets was excluded.

247

248 The ecoinvent database heat and power production activities apply an exergy-based allocation, assigning a larger
249 share of environmental impact to electricity due to its higher exergy value. Given the heat-led nature of our studied
250 system, an energy-based allocation was deemed more appropriate. When considering electricity expressed in kWh
251 and heat in MJ, OpenModelica simulations indicate a relatively stable hydrogen consumption split of 83.93% to
252 electricity and 16.07% to heat, which was used to allocate flows accordingly. Lubricating oil flow was estimated
253 based on a typical value of 0.025 [0.01-0.05] × 10⁻³ kg/MJ of fuel input, which translates into 2.997 [1.1988 -
254 5.994] 10⁻³ kg / kg H₂. Biosphere flows related to natural gas in the original dataset were removed, except for
255 nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM). Although H₂ combustion can increase NO_x emissions, ultra-
256 lean conditions ($\lambda = 2.6$) at 1500 rpm in the model allow to postulate very low NO_x emissions (Sterlepper et al.,
257 2021; Verhelst & Wallner, 2009; Heffel, 2003), justifying a conservative emission assumption of 10–50 ppm. PM
258 emissions, primarily originating from lubricating oil (Worton et al., 2014), were scaled using the PM-to-lubricating
259 oil ratio from the ecoinvent dataset. Due to CHP modulation mode in the OpenModelica model, annual electricity
260 and heat yields vary by scenario, dynamically affecting ICE-CHP unit consumption based on an assumed 25-year
261 lifetime.

262

263 Since the ICE-CHP is the endpoint of H₂ mass flows, this component completely integrates the modeling of the
264 PEMEL and H2C components through its fuel supply – see **Section 3.6**. PEMEL and H2C thus don't appear
265 directly in the contribution analysis in **Section 4.2**, unlike the H2S component modeled as an infrastructure with
266 an annual unit consumption.

267

268 **3.4. ELECTRICAL SYSTEM**

269

270 **3.4.1. PV – Photovoltaic**

271 We adopted a mixed approach regarding PV construction/decommission of 0.9 and 1.8 MWp PV installations
272 present in the investigated scenarios. Indeed, flows associated to the mounting system and the panel wafers are
273 expected to vary linearly with installed capacity. We controlled this assumption by the analysis of the following
274 ecoinvent activities when normalized to 1 kWp:

- 275 • *“photovoltaic slanted-roof installation, 3 kWp, multi-Si, panel, mounted, on roof (CH)”*
- 276 • *“photovoltaic plant construction, 570 kWp, multi-Si, on open ground (GLO)”*

277

278 The normalized flow ratios for the two sub-components of the PV system were both 0.987, indicating only a 1.3%
279 flow reduction as installed capacity increased from 3 to 570 kWp. For these flows, linear scaling was applied. In
280 contrast, other PV sub-components exhibited non-linear scaling with capacity, and each was adjusted using a
281 dedicated b coefficient, following the method of Zhang et al. (2017) – see **Appendix**. Additionally, the *“market
282 for electricity, low voltage”* dataset for Switzerland (CH) was replaced with its German (DE) equivalent. All base
283 datasets used already include end-of-life processes.

284

285 The resulting PV electricity production process was based on the *“electricity production, photovoltaic, 3 kWp
286 slanted-roof installation, multi-Si, panel, mounted (low voltage, DE)”* ecoinvent activity. We adapted the flow for
287 the consumption of our 0.9 or 1.8 MWp PV unit based on the annual yields provided by the OpenModelica
288 simulation, while keeping the same projected lifetime (30 years). The *“market for tap water (EUR, CH excluded)”*
289 activity, representing the cleaning of the PV panels, was scaled linearly.

290

291 3.4.2. WT – Wind turbine

292 The construction and decommissioning of WT was modeled using the ecoinvent activity “*wind power plant*
293 *construction, 800 kW (fixed + moving parts, GLO)*” as a reference. To adapt this process to a 500 kW WT, scaling
294 was performed following a phenomenological approach adapting the method of Zhang et al. (2017), described in
295 the previous section. A scaling factor $b = 0.83$ was determined through interpolation (Eq. 3) of impact scores
296 derived from three ecoinvent datasets:

- 297 • “*wind power plant construction, 800 kW (fixed+moving parts, GLO)*”
- 298 • “*wind turbine construction, 750 kW (GLO)*”
- 299 • “*wind turbine construction, small-scale, 6 kW (DE)*”

300

301 This factor ensures consistency between the impact results of resulting 500 kW dataset and the trends observed in
302 the available ecoinvent datasets. One WT unit of 500 kW is thus considered equivalent to 0.677 WT unit of the
303 800 kW WT. A triangular uncertainty was set on this coefficient based on the linear scaling case ($b = 1$) and the
304 estimation from the comparison of exact technosphere matches for the 6, 750, 800 kW WT datasets ($b = 0.74$).

305

306 The operational electricity generation by the WT was modeled using the “*electricity production, wind, <1 MW*
307 *turbine, onshore (high voltage, DE)*” activity. The unit consumption was adjusted to match the annual electricity
308 yield from the 500 kW WT unit simulated in OpenModelica, assuming a 20-year service life. Voltage
309 transformation losses from high to low voltage were accounted for using a coefficient of 0.9635, based on the
310 “*electricity voltage transformation*” processes available in ecoinvent.

311

312 3.4.3. BAT – Battery

313 Battery production was modeled using the activity “*market for battery, Li-ion, NMC811, rechargeable, prismatic*
314 *(GLO)*”, linearly scaled to reflect a 500 kWh BAT. This scaling was based on the reported specific energy density
315 of 0.149 kWh/kg. End-of-life treatment was approximated using the “*market for used Li-ion battery (GLO)*”
316 activity, scaled identically.

317

318 Since no explicit use-phase activity exists in the ecoinvent database, we developed a custom use-phase model
319 derived from the OpenModelica simulation results. As energy losses are already accounted for, our use-phase
320 modeling calculates the unit consumption per kWh stored and retrieved (Porzio & Scown, 2021). This was done
321 through a scenario-wide analysis of battery-related variables, including state of charge (SoC) evolution and
322 charge/discharge behavior. The SoC evolution was relatively consistent within scenario families, with values
323 typically ranging between 0.19 and 0.69. Although extreme SoC values (e.g., 0.10 and 0.90) were occasionally
324 reached, the majority of operation remained in the mid-range window, yielding an average usable capacity of 49.7
325 $\pm 0.3\%$ of the installed BAT. Similarly, distributions of charge/discharge rates (C-rates) showed little variance
326 across scenarios, with a standard deviation of 0.33 ± 0.06 . However, average C-rate values differed: “WT + BAT”
327 scenario family showed a mean C-rate of 0.14, while those including PV had higher values, between 0.36 and
328 0.38. This difference reflects the increased use of storage capacity in PV scenarios due to the system’s electricity
329 overproduction. These patterns correspond to low to moderate operational stress, suggesting favorable battery
330 longevity. Therefore, we adopted a projected lifetime of 2600 ± 1000 full equivalent cycles to 80% of initial
331 capacity, which is consistent with high-end estimates for NMC811 chemistries (Preger et al., 2020; Ecker et al.,
332 2014). Assuming full cycles defined between 10% and 90% SoC, the expected total energy throughput over the
333 battery’s life was calculated to define the unit consumption per kWh discharged, with a triangular uncertainty.

334

335 3.5. HEATING SYSTEM

336

337 3.5.1. GSHP – Ground source heat pump

338 Heat pump production was modeled using the ecoinvent datasets “*heat pump production, brine-water, 10 kW*
339 *(CH)*” and “*borehole heat exchanger production, 150 m (CH)*”, linearly scaled to reflect a 197 kW GSHP in the
340 absence of data for scaling. When applicable, process geographies were replaced with German equivalents. The

341 heat pump dataset includes manufacturing and partial end-of-life (plastics disposal via “*market for waste plastic,*
342 *mixture*”), which was removed. A separate “treatment of heat pump” activity was created, covering copper, steel,
343 refrigerant, and PVC waste flows. The borehole component was assumed to remain in place at end-of-life due to
344 limited data and practical constraints. Heat production modeling used the “*heat production, borehole heat*
345 *exchanger, brine-water heat pump 10 kW (CH)*” activity, supplemented with the added disposal flow. Electricity
346 use per MJ of heat was taken from the OpenModelica simulation.

347

348 3.5.2. TES – Thermal energy storage

349 This system component is absent from the flow exchanges in the scenarios modeled in the OpenModelica
350 simulation, despite being present as an available infrastructure. We thus decided to consider it absent in our study.

351

352 3.6. HYDROGEN SYSTEM

353

354 3.6.1. PEMEL – Proton exchange membrane electrolyzer

355 The electrolyzer component was based on the LCI from Gerloff (2021), harmonizing previous datasets and scaled
356 for a 1 MW system using Zhang et al. (2016) method described in **Section 3.3**. We applied the same approach to
357 construct and decommission our 0.5 MW PEMEL, using scaling coefficients of 0.7 for Balance of Plant and 0.88
358 for Stack flows. Hydrogen production was also based on Gerloff (2021), using the premise library version with
359 uncertainties (Sacchi et al., 2022). Variations accounted for different electricity sources from the OpenModelica
360 model. Electricity consumption per kg H₂ was taken from the simulation, with a 10% triangular uncertainty
361 reflecting deviations in Beerlage et al. (2024). Water use in the model includes only stoichiometric needs, while
362 Gerloff’s LCI accounts for additional real-world use (cooling, etc.), increasing water consumption by 55%. We
363 thus scaled OpenModelica water consumption accordingly.

364

365 3.6.2. H2C – Hydrogen compressor

366 The compressor component was modeled using the cradle-to-grave LCI from Ghandehariun & Kumar (2016), with
367 German (DE) flows applied when possible. Electricity consumption per kg of H₂ compressed was adjusted based
368 on OpenModelica simulation data. Since electricity demand depends on the hourly state of hydrogen storage, the
369 annual apparent electricity consumption (kWh/kg H₂ compressed) varies across scenarios.

370

371 3.6.3. H2S – Hydrogen storage

372 Hydrogen is stored as gas at a maximum of 80 bar in various sizes – **Table 1**. The LCI is based on the ecoinvent
373 “*storage production, 10,000 l*” activity, representing 10 m³. This dataset includes end-of-life flows and assumes
374 100,000 hours of operation (about 11–12 years). We updated this to 20 years to align with the OpenModelica
375 simulation and derived annual unit consumption accordingly. Other storage sizes were linearly scaled.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. LCIA MONTE CARLO RESULTS

Figure 3 summarises the results of the impacts calculated for the different 28 scenarios, per scenario family and per impact perimeter considered. H₂ storage capacities (H₂S) within each scenario family evolve as described previously in **Section 2.3, Table 2**.

4.1.1. 'Load' boundary Monte Carlo

In this case, only the flows directly fulfilling the heat and electricity demand of the Offenburg buildings are considered. Due to uncertainties, no clear conclusion can be drawn regarding human toxicity (carcinogenic) or ecotoxicity (freshwater) impacts across scenarios. These impacts mostly hover near zero, except for the unrealistic H₂S = 1000 m³ cases, which show greater result variability. For climate change and resource consumption, 'WT + BAT' scenarios consistently show higher impacts than those with PV. The highest impacts occur at H₂S = 1 and 1000 m³, while capacities between 10 and 100 m³ yield the lowest, with no significant differences within this range in the same scenario family. Water use impacts follow a similar pattern, with 'PV + WT + BAT' scenarios generally having the lowest values. Since the 10–100 m³ H₂S range is the only realistic option, it can be concluded that H₂S dimensioning in real conditions likely has minimal effect on environmental performance, with scenario family playing a larger role. This is supported by subsequent cases showing near-flat impact trends and differences mainly due to scenario families and uncertainties.

4.1.2. 'Load + Excess' boundary Monte Carlo

When the system's excess electricity – actually produced but not used by the Offenburg buildings – is included in the environmental assessment, the overall scenario family ranking is reversed. The 'WT + BAT' scenarios now show the lowest environmental impacts across all categories and exhibit less result variability than PV-including alternatives, due to low electricity overproduction reported in **Section 3.2**. This family uniquely displays negligible human toxicity (carcinogenic) and ecotoxicity (freshwater) impacts and is also the only one where the unrealistic H₂S = 1000 m³ scenario causes a notable increase in both impact and uncertainty. Within PV-including scenarios, two subgroups emerge: those with 0.9 MW installed PV ('PV + WT + BAT') and those with 1.8 MW ('PV + BAT' and 'PV'). The latter group produces almost identical results across categories, except for slightly lower resource use impacts in the BAT-excluded scenarios. Meanwhile, the 'PV + WT + BAT' family occupies a middle ground in both impact level and dispersion. As noted in **Section 3.2**, PV-heavy scenarios generate considerable electricity surpluses fed into the GRID. These findings support a second key conclusion: in H₂ ICE-CHP-based DES, how excess electricity is accounted for can fundamentally alter the comparative evaluation of scenarios.

4.1.3. 'Load + Excess - Grid(DE)' boundary Monte Carlo

When excess electricity is assumed to be fed into the GRID and replaces electricity that would otherwise be produced by the German electricity mix, the resulting avoided impacts are considered. In this third assessment boundary, the environmental burden of the electricity overproduction is subtracted from the total ('Load + Excess') by modeling these kWh as if they had been generated using the national mix. Because the German grid mix is currently associated with high impacts across all categories, PV-including scenarios – producing large electricity surpluses – lead to substantial avoided impacts, especially in climate change, resource consumption, and water use. Among these, scenarios based solely on PV (in addition to the ICE-CHP) result in greater avoided impacts than the 'PV + WT + BAT' family, due to higher installed PV capacity. However, this benefit comes at the cost of increased result dispersion. In particular, the human toxicity (carcinogenic) and ecotoxicity (freshwater) categories exhibit wide uncertainty ranges nearly centered around zero, making the interpretation of avoided impacts in these categories less reliable.

424
 425 **Figure 3.** Environmental impacts with uncertainties of the H₂-based energy system, by scenario family. Within
 426 each family, progression follows decreasing H₂ storage capacity in m³ (1000, 500, 100, 50, 30, 10, 1). The rows
 427 represent the environmental category tested. Columns represent the impact boundary. The solid lines represent the
 428 median values of the Monte Carlo simulations. The dotted lines delimit the quartiles ± 25% around the median
 429 values.
 430
 431

432

433 **4.1.4. LCIA results synthesis**

434 The **Table 3** provides a synthetic presentation of the global results (scenarios aggregated) for the realistic H2S
 435 values – i.e. H2S = 10–100 m³. It highlights how the system boundaries considered highly shift the interpretation
 436 that can be made on the environmental impacts.

437 **Table 3.** Overview of the LCIA results for the decentralized ‘stand-alone’ energy system based on H₂ ICE-CHP.

Impact Indicator	Unit	Load	Load + Excess	Load + Excess - Grid (DE)
GWP100	(kg CO ₂ eq) [$\cdot 10^3$]	67.5 ± 33	832 ± 129	-96532 ± 5526
ECOTOX-FW	(CTUe) [$\cdot 10^3$]	633 ± 465	80287 ± 24462	-418538 ± 385035
HTOX-C	(CTUh) [$\cdot 10^{-4}$]	4.8 ± 2.5	152 ± 86	-2360 ± 2471
ADP-UR	(kg Sb eq)	1.36 ± 0,21	10.6 ± 2,2	-1311.3 ± 361,1
UDP-WU	(m ³ world eq deprived) [$\cdot 10^3$]	34 ± 7	6228 ± 2819	-20072 ± 3927

438

439 **4.2. CONTRIBUTION ANALYSIS**

440

441 **Figure 4** summarises the results of the contribution analysis for the different 28 scenarios, per scenario family and
 442 per impact perimeter considered. H₂ storage capacities (H2S) within each scenario family evolve as described
 443 previously in **Section 2.3, Table 2**.

444

445 **4.2.1. ‘Load’ boundary contributions**

446 Excluding excess electricity from the assessment enables a focused analysis of subsystem contributions to meeting
 447 the heat and electricity demands of Offenburg’s buildings. In this context, the ICE-CHP component – grouped
 448 with PEMEL and H2C due to the modeling structure – shows its lowest contribution (~3%) in the climate change
 449 and human toxicity (carcinogenic) categories, and its highest (~38%) in human toxicity (carcinogenic), ecotoxicity
 450 (freshwater), and water use. Within the realistic H2S = [10-100] m³ range, ICE-CHP contributions remain stable
 451 across PV-including scenarios (normalized standard deviation, N_{std} = 2–5%), except for human toxicity
 452 (carcinogenic), where variability increases to ~21%. In contrast, this category’s N_{std} drops to ~2% in the ‘WT +
 453 BAT’ family, while other families range between 8–13%.

454

455 Most of other subsystems (PV, WT, BAT, GSHP, GRID) follow similar patterns in this realistic H2S interval.
 456 Their contribution variability is highest in the human toxicity (carcinogenic) category (N_{std} = 12–31%), with larger
 457 deviations linked to PV presence. For the remaining environmental categories, variability remains low (N_{std} = 1–
 458 8%) across scenarios. PV reaches its maximum contribution (~16%) in water use and its minimum (~0.3%) in
 459 resource consumption. WT, by contrast, has a minimum contribution (1–2%) consistent across categories – except
 460 for a ~3% minimum contribution in resource consumption – and its maximum of ~23% is found in human toxicity
 461 (carcinogenic). BAT, GSHP, and GRID reach their lowest contributions (0.6–2%) in this same environmental
 462 category. BAT share peaks (~33%) in resource consumption, while GSHP and GRID show maximum
 463 contributions in climate change (~47% and ~59%, respectively).

464

465 H2S minimal contribution is consistently below 0.3% across several environmental categories but reaches a
 466 maximum of ~92% in human toxicity (carcinogenic). Even in the realistic H2S [10–100] m³ interval, contribution
 467 variability remains high with complex interplays. For resource consumption, N_{std} changes between ~59% (with
 468 BAT) and ~83% (without BAT). For human toxicity (carcinogenic), N_{std} depends mostly on PV, increasing from
 469 ~59% in ‘WT+BAT’ scenario family to ~71% in PV-including scenarios. In contrast, variability for climate
 470 change, ecotoxicity (freshwater), and water use is relatively stable, with N_{std} around ~81%, ~76%, and ~79%,
 471 respectively.

472

473 A synthesis of the results for the realistic interval of H2S values is given in **Table 4**. Overall, ICE-CHP, GSHP
 474 and GRID tend to be key contributors to the impact across all environmental categories, while PV, WT, BAT, and

475 H2S reach significant contribution in only one or two categories out of five, each of them exhibiting a different
 476 configuration.

477
 478 **Table 4.** Average contributions (in percentages) to the impact on the H2S = [10–100] m³ interval, across families
 479 of scenarios for the ‘Load’ boundary.

Contributor	GWP100	ECOTOX-FW	HTOX-C	ADP-UR	UDP-WU
ICE-CHP	12.3 ± 3.6	33.2 ± 6.4	29.0 ± 6.3	21.4 ± 3.0	29.0 ± 7.2
PV	1.0 ± 0.2	10.0 ± 2.2	2.9 ± 1.4	0.5 ± 0.1	13.1 ± 2.4
WT	3.0 ± 0.1	6.6 ± 1.7	15.1 ± 2.6	4.0 ± 0.7	3.4 ± 1.1
BAT	4.9 ± 2.0	8.8 ± 2.4	6.9 ± 1.3	23.4 ± 10.7	17.1 ± 6.6
GSHP	30.4 ± 3.0	20.6 ± 2.6	17.4 ± 3.9	26.2 ± 2.3	20.0 ± 3.1
H2S	2.9 ± 2.5	6.0 ± 4.5	23.7 ± 16.9	0.5 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 1.5
GRID	48.6 ± 8.2	22.7 ± 8.8	15.1 ± 7.3	32.1 ± 13.0	24.6 ± 11.9

480
 481 **4.2.2. ‘Load + Excess’ boundary contributions**

482 The reversal in scenario ranking between the L and L+E boundaries stems from differing levels of electricity
 483 overproduction. In the ‘WT + BAT’ cases, excess electricity is limited, contributing only 20–25% to the total
 484 impact. This keeps results relatively stable across boundaries. In contrast, PV-based scenarios generate far more
 485 electricity than required, with overproduction electricity sometimes representing up to 99% of the total impact.
 486 **Table 5** summarizes outcomes for the realistic H2S values.

487
 488 **Table 5.** Average contributions (in percentages) to the impact on the H2S = [10–100] m³ interval, per families of
 489 scenarios for the ‘Load + Excess’ boundary. Families only comprising PV (apart from the ICE-CHP) were
 490 aggregated due to the proximity of the results.

Scenario family	Contributor	GWP100	ECOTOX-FW	HTOX-C	ADP-UR	UDP-WU
PV + WT + BAT	Load	9.8 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1	6.1 ± 1.2	14.6 ± 0.3	0.90 ± 0.02
	Excess	90.2 ± 0.2	98.7 ± 0.1	93.9 ± 1.2	85.4 ± 0.3	99.10 ± 0.02
WT + BAT	Load	98.5 ± 1.2	95.8 ± 3.3	92.9 ± 5.8	96.1 ± 3.0	96.3 ± 2.8
	Excess	1.6 ± 1.2	4.2 ± 3.3	7.1 ± 5.8	3.9 ± 3.0	3.7 ± 2.8
PV + BAT & PV	Load	4.1 ± 0.1	0.41 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.4	7.2 ± 0.2	0.32 ± 0.01
	Excess	95.9 ± 0.1	99.6 ± 0.02	98.7 ± 0.4	92.8 ± 0.2	99.68 ± 0.01

491
 492 **4.2.3. ‘Load + Excess - Grid(DE)’ boundary contributions**

493 When avoided impacts are considered, the ratio of the H₂-ICE-CHP-based DES impacts to avoided German mix
 494 impacts ranges from 120–200 for climate change, 4–10 for freshwater ecotoxicity, 14–23 for human toxicity
 495 (carcinogenic), 130–160 for resource use, and 3–7 for water use. Even in the context of a French case study, these
 496 benefits are likely to occur, despite the French electricity mix being significantly cleaner. Indeed, the
 497 French/Germany electricity mix impact ratios for these environmental categories are respectively 0.22; 0.41; 0.53;
 498 0.85; 1.42 (ecoinvent v3.10), suggesting an environmental benefit in the order of magnitude of 27–44 for climate
 499 change, 2–4 for freshwater ecotoxicity, 7–12 for human toxicity (carcinogenic), 110–136 for resource use, and 4–
 500 10 for water use. However, these results should be considered with caution. As the electricity mix gets cleaner,
 501 the decline of the environmental burden will induce a reduction of the avoided impacts as calculated here. This
 502 shift could be explored in future prospective LCAs, pending availability of national scenarios in tools like the
 503 premise library (Sacchi et al. 2022). Moreover, large electricity overproduction may strain the grid if demand isn’t
 504 present when transfer occurs. Although the TEA OpenModelica simulations had hourly resolution, the impact
 505 assessment integrates results annually and assumes uninterrupted transfer to the grid throughout the year.
 506

507
 508 **Figure 4.** Subsystem contributions to the impact of the H₂-based energy system, by scenario family. Within each
 509 scenario family, progression is by decreasing H₂ storage capacity in m³ (1000, 500, 100, 50, 30, 10, 1). The rows
 510 represent the environmental category tested. The columns represent the impact boundary. In the “Load + Excess -
 511 Grid (DE)” column, the avoided impacts (negative values) of GRID are normalized to the sum of “Load + Excess”.
 512

513 4.2.4. Contribution analysis synthesis

514 Within the ‘Load’ boundary, the GRID component’s dominance across environmental categories suggests that
515 system-level optimization should prioritize reducing reliance on the German electricity mix year-round. Due to
516 substantial electricity overproduction at certain times, two complementary strategies are proposed. For short-term
517 LOAD demand fluctuations, increased short-term storage is needed, implying a larger BAT component. For
518 seasonal variations, greater long-term storage is required, necessitating an expanded H₂ system. Indeed, fully using
519 electricity overproduction first requires scaling up the PEMEL to produce more H₂. Given the low environmental
520 impact of H₂S (as shown in **Table 4**), maximizing its capacity is recommended. Stored H₂ quantity can be further
521 increased by raising compression from 80 to 200 bar, following industrial norms, with additional electricity
522 required sourced from overproduction. Using the supplementary H₂ would also require a larger ICE-CHP. Future
523 TEA simulations with OpenModelica should examine these scenarios for feasibility and enable further LCA
524 comparisons, advancing multi-criteria and multi-boundary optimization.

525 4.3. GLOBAL SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

526 The Activity Browser software has a dedicated module for global sensitivity analysis (GSA) computations which
527 is based on the δ -measure (Cucurachi et al. 2021, Borgonovo & Apostolakis, 2001). The δ value quantifies how
528 much the variation of a given process is able to move the results distribution. This module was used to perform
529 GSA upon the Monte Carlo simulations for each scenario and impact indicator, with a cut-off value of 0.01 for
530 both the technosphere and biosphere.
531

532 4.3.1. Rank correlation and sets similarity

533 An initial analysis of GSA results used Kendall’s τ coefficient (Kendall, 1938) to assess how process δ values rank
534 across scenarios. Most τ values fell within [-0.1, 0.2], indicating weak correlation in process influence across
535 scenarios. Two exceptions were water use and ecotoxicity (freshwater) in the L+E boundary, though their complex
536 patterns are beyond this study’s scope. Overall, the low correlation is likely due to many processes having similar
537 δ values, allowing small differences to shift their ranking between scenarios.
538

539 We thus used a cruder indicator, the Jaccard similarity index (Jaccard, 1912), insensitive to ranking, to map
540 sensitivity across scenarios. **Figure 5** highlights clear patterns of similarity and divergence. Under the *L* boundary,
541 most scenarios within the same family show low similarity in process-level sensitivity, except for those in the H₂S
542 = 10–100 m³ interval, which display higher overlap – consistent with **Section 4.2.1**’s findings of minimal variation
543 in contributors. Boundaries expansion (*L+E* and *L+E-G*) reveal a clearer separation of the ‘WT + BAT’ scenarios
544 from the other families, driven by the role of PV and GRID in contribution variability, as discussed in **Sections**
545 **4.2.2** and **4.2.3**.

546
 547
 548
 549

Figure 5. Jaccard similarity across scenarios for the hydrogen-based energy system. Values near 1 indicate strong overlap between GSA outputs by pairs of scenarios, while values near 0 indicate low overlap.

550 **4.3.2. Spread of δ values and maximums**

551 Given the sensitivity of contributing processes and their δ values, it is useful to examine both the maximum and
 552 range (max–min) of δ , by process and overall. **Table 6** summarizes global statistics across boundaries, scenario
 553 families, and impact indicators. Overall, aggregation choices yield similar δ value statistics.

554 **Table 6.** Global statistics of the δ values resulting from the GSA. Values are scaled by a 10^2 factor for readability.

	Aggregation	Mean	Median	Std	Min	Max
Boundary	Load	6.7-7.5	6.3-7.0	1.7-6.6	1.3-2.8	13.2-70.1
	Load + Excess	6.8-13.7	6.6-7.4	1.7-21.2	1.1-4.1	13.6-78.0
	Load + Excess - Grid (DE)	6.8-7.9	6.6-7.2	1.7-4.9	1.3-3.3	12.6-47.2
Scenario Family	PV + WT + BAT	6.7-11.8	6.3-7.2	1.7-18.4	1.3-3.2	12.7-76.3
	WT + BAT	6.8-7.2	6.6-7.0	1.7-3.0	1.4-2.5	13.5-48.6
	PV + BAT	6.8-13.5	6.6-7.3	1.7-21.2	1.8-4.1	12.6-78.0
	PV	6.8-13.7	6.5-7.4	1.7-21.2	1.1-3.7	13.6-77.6
Impact Indicator	GWP100	6.7-7.9	6.3-7.1	2.1-4.9	1.1-2.8	22.2-48.6
	ECOTOX-FW	7.0-9.0	6.8-7.4	1.7-6.3	1.3-4.1	13.1-35.2
	HTOX-C	6.8-7.2	6.7-7.1	1.7-2.1	1.5-2.9	12.6-27.2
	ADP-UR	6.8-7.2	6.6-6.9	2.1-4.0	1.4-2.7	23.7-41.4
	UDP-WU	6.8-13.7	6.6-7.2	2.2-21.2	1.4-3.7	23.3-78.0

555

556 Greater dispersion of δ values is found in the *L+E* boundary, especially in PV-based scenarios and particularly for
 557 the water use category. A standout flow is the biosphere flow “*Water // electricity production, from 0.9/1.8 MW*
 558 *PV*” representing PV panel cleaning, which shows the highest δ values (up to 0.70–0.80), while the other flows
 559 are limited to δ values ≤ 0.50 . Furthermore, this flow has low δ spread ($\delta = 0.74$ – 0.78) within *L+E* boundary,
 560 making it the clear dominant source of results variability in water in this case. Its influence remains under the *L+E-*
 561 *G* boundary ($\delta = 0.16$ – 0.38), and becomes highly fluctuant within the *L* boundary ($\delta = 0.43$ – 0.70), reflecting the
 562 differing role of PV across scenarios and boundaries. Actual needs for panel cleaning are highly susceptible to
 563 local conditions of the PV infrastructure, thus field experiments should allow better tailoring of the LCA model.
 564 Outside this exception, processes with high δ values often show the widest spreads, as seen in **Figure 6**. The
 565 technosphere flow “*reinforcing steel // storage production, 10,000 l*” (H₂S annual unit consumption) has the
 566 broadest δ range and second-highest δ values, with spreads of 0.42 (climate change) and 0.34 (water use), and δ
 567 peaks of 0.46-0.48 and 0.36-0.39, respectively. This is mainly because the dataset is old, which leads to a wide
 568 distribution of possible values within the uncertainties quantified by the pedigree matrix approach. Other
 569 influential elements include flows tied to the German electricity mix (e.g., “CO₂ [...] lignite/hard coal”
 570 “distribution network”, “copper cathode”, “Anthracene”) or GSHP production, which we modeled as produced in
 571 Germany thus also related to the German mix. The uncertainty in the German mix dataset stems from the inherent
 572 complexity of large-scale systems like a national electricity grid. It is further compounded by the use of annual
 573 temporal averaging for national mixes that includes diverse electricity generation technologies, which is associated
 574 to high variations of impact throughout the year. In this context, using a representative dynamic dataset of the
 575 annual German electricity mix could reduce the associated uncertainties.

576 Thus, the top two contributors to LCIA variability (water use for PV panel cleaning & steel for H₂S unit
 577 production) are driven by the foreground scenario, while most others are linked to background data uncertainties.
 578 A few dominant processes, whose importance varies along foreground scenarios, shape variability in water use,
 579 climate change, and resource consumption. Conversely, human toxicity (carcinogenic) and ecotoxicity
 580 (freshwater) indicators depend on a broader set of processes with individually smaller influence.

581
 582 **Figure 6.** Processes with the highest spread of δ values across scenarios and impact indicators, per scenario family
 583 and boundary. Prefixes T/B respectively indicate a technosphere or biosphere flow.
 584

585 4.4. TEA-LCA OPEN-SOURCE CONTRIBUTION

586 As outlined in the **Introduction** section, this study also investigated the integration or combined use of techno-
 587 economic assessment (TEA) and life cycle assessment (LCA) for localized, multi-criteria evaluations using open-
 588 source tools. A recent publication synthesized ten key recommendations for research software in the energy
 589 domain (Ferenz et al., 2025). The publication identify a typical profile of energy researchers, which corresponds
 590 to the authors of the present study – scientists from diverse disciplinary backgrounds without formal training in
 591 software engineering. Among the Ferenz et al. recommendations, numbers 2, 4 9, and 10 pertain to medium to
 592 long-term software development practices and are thus outside the scope of the current work. The remaining
 593 recommendations are directly relevant and addressed in this section. These include: (1) reusing and extending
 594 existing software when possible; (3) ensuring openness and findability of the software; (5) considering reusability
 595 of research software; (6) maintaining a simple architecture; (7) providing thorough documentation; and (8)
 596 conducting adequate software testing.

597
 598 A widely accessible overview of process simulators used in engineering and research is available on Wikipedia
 599 (2025). However, only ~8% of listed tools are fully open-source, and even fewer support full interoperability (3).
 600 For TEA-LCA integration, tools must be general-purpose and flexible (5), which to the authors’ knowledge
 601 narrows viable candidates to Pyomo and OpenModelica. Given in-house expertise and time constraints, the TEA
 602 model was developed using the Modelica language and OpenModelica compiler (1). The resulting simulation
 603 model is modular and scalable (6), supporting integration of diverse energy producers, consumers, and storage
 604 technologies. It is openly available on GitHub with initial documentation (3, 7) – see **Appendix**. Nonetheless,
 605 OpenModelica presents specific challenges. Internally, limited documentation and programming support (7) led
 606 to unexplained compiler failures and debugging difficulties. Externally, integration with platforms like Brightway
 607 or Activity Browser is feasible but hampered by language incompatibilities, complicating workflows (6).
 608

609 To address interoperability issues (1, 5, 6), this work contributes modular Python procedures that: clean and
 610 preprocess OpenModelica outputs; extract relevant variables for the H₂-based ICE-CHP DES model; allocate
 611 energy and mass flows across any number of modeled scenarios – see **Section 3.2**. These procedures are embedded
 612 in Jupyter Notebooks, supporting internal documentation and reproducibility with verification computations
 613 available within (7). They were tested across scenarios of increasing complexity to ensure robustness (8). All
 614 materials are openly available via GitHub – see **Appendix** (3). Furthermore, **Sections 3.3–3.6** describe how scaling
 615 factors were derived for most infrastructure components to align LCI datasets with the ecoinvent database, with
 616 thorough documentation available from the repositories linked in **Appendix** (7). Although not open-source,

617 ecoinvent was selected for its general applicability and widespread use in LCA (1, 3). However, due to limitations
618 in Activity Browser documentation (7) and programming capacity, modifying infrastructure and operational flows
619 in LCA still requires manual input. Future work by more proficient developers could build on the current Python
620 modules to enable automatic integration between OpenModelica and the Activity Browser GUI for Brightway,
621 potentially via scenario-specific foreground flow-exchange files (1, 5).

622
623 A long-term, more robust solution would likely involve the development of a fully Python-based TEA-LCA
624 modeling framework (6), following precedents in biorefinery simulation (Shi & Guest, 2020). This would support
625 a transition toward Pyomo, a Python-native optimization library well-aligned with Brightway2 (1, 3). Pyomo
626 underpins 18% of open-source tools listed by the Open Energy Modelling Initiative (Openmod, 2025), including
627 the very recent AdOpT-NET0 (Wiegner et al., 2025), which targets multi-energy system optimization. Exploring
628 its integration with Brightway2 offers a promising avenue for future TEA-LCA research (1, 5).

5. CONCLUSIONS

629

630 This study provides a thorough LCA of a H₂-based DES using an ICE-CHP, covering building demands under
631 multiple scenarios based on real data of the Offenburg city (Germany). By combining TEA modeling in
632 OpenModelica with customized Python procedures and a transparent LCA approach with Brightway/Activity
633 Browser, we have contributed to the effort towards reproducible frameworks for open source multi-criteria
634 sustainability assessment of complex energy systems at the local scale. Two specific methodological contributions
635 call for further optimization: (a) flow allocation routines, to use when flows between system's components are not
636 explicit outputs of the TEA simulation, and (b) scaling factors for adapting infrastructure sizes in new scenarios –
637 focusing on consistency with the ecoinvent database.

638 Wide distributions of results are observed, even though 50% of the values are comparatively more tightly clustered.
639 Through Monte Carlo sampling for uncertainty computation and Global Sensitivity Analysis, we found an
640 unexpected weight of PV panel cleaning in the water use category. This process showed the highest δ values in
641 the global sensitivity analysis, highlighting its outsized influence on results variability. The GSA also revealed that
642 foreground scenario structure (e.g., presence of PV or sizing of H₂S) and background database uncertainty jointly
643 shape impact variability with distinct influences through lack of: regionalization (water for PV cleaning); recent
644 data (H₂S production); and dynamic accounting (German electricity mix contributors). A key insight from the
645 GSA was that different environmental categories are dominated by different patterns: climate change, water use,
646 and resource consumption are driven by a small number of dominant processes, while toxicity-related categories
647 are shaped by a more diverse and diffuse set of contributors. The Jaccard similarity index allowed us to track how
648 scenario family structure and selected system/impact boundaries correlates with the importance of these
649 parameters in scenario comparisons.

650 Uncertainty and sensitivity elements considered, several findings emerge. The ICE-CHP system, incorporating
651 PEMEL and H₂C, contributed modestly to climate change category but can have an unneglectable burden in other
652 environmental categories, highlighting that local actors should not only strive for CO₂ eq emissions reduction at
653 the optimum cost, which is often their main focus, but also pay attention to other environmental categories.
654 Unrealistic scenarios excepted, the hydrogen storage component generally had a negligible environmental
655 footprint – especially in the climate change, ecotoxicity, and human toxicity categories.

656 Scenario family composition (PV, WT, BAT) was found to be a far more influential parameter than hydrogen
657 storage size. In particular, the inclusion of PV infrastructure consistently led to higher electricity overproduction,
658 which significantly altered environmental impacts depending on whether or how excess electricity was considered
659 (boundary influence). When electricity overproduction is not considered, WT-based systems perform worse across
660 impact categories. Conversely, when including overproduction, the environmental burden of PV becomes more
661 apparent due to its disproportionate contribution linked to electricity overproduction that exceeds local demand.
662 However, if this surplus is assumed to replace conventional German electricity in external uses, PV-comprising
663 scenarios lead to the most avoided impacts, especially in categories like climate change and resource use. These
664 benefits are contingent on the current impact of the electricity mix and postulate total transfer throughout the year,
665 which may not be true depending on the grid stability due to increasing intermittent renewable energies. Based on
666 our present findings, development policies of this kind of decentralized energy systems should thus be careful of
667 system/impact boundaries selected when environmental benefits are reported and plan installations carefully to
668 also anticipate and minimize pressure on the grid.

669 To conclude, while expected real-world applications of H₂ ICE-CHP systems appear environmentally interesting
670 under realistic storage sizing, the environmental performance is highly dependent on scenario design, electricity
671 overproduction consideration, and underlying database assumptions. The methodological open-source workflow
672 developed here in the context of the Interreg CO₂InnO project – though still limited by requiring manual adaptation
673 for LCA – should be scaled and automated in future research. Developing a fully Python-based bridge between
674 OpenModelica and Activity Browser, or a new integrated tool, would allow streamlined and automated analysis
675 for broader TEA-LCA analysis. Our findings are relevant for the TEA-LCA community as well as for actors of
676 local energy policies.

APPENDIX

677

678 The TEA model developed (Beerlage et al., 2024) is available at the following GitHub URL:

679

- <https://github.com/IKKUengine/CO2InnO-H2-CHP-Demonstrator>

680

681 The Jupyter Notebooks embedding the Python modular procedures for TEA model results processing and
682 reconstruction of inter sub-systems' flows for LCA models are available at the following GitHub and Zenodo
683 URLs, with the Zenodo repository hosting the full datasets at all stages, and the GitHub repository hosting only
the cleaned and processed datasets:

684

- <https://github.com/Paul-Robineau/Processing-CO2InnO-H2-CHP-Demonstrator-outputs>

685

- <https://zenodo.org/records/16919026>

686

687 The Jupyter Notebooks embedding the Python modular procedures for LCA data processing and visualization are
available at the following GitHub and Zenodo URLs, both hosting the full datasets:

688

- <https://github.com/Paul-Robineau/LCA-ScenarioResults-from-CO2InnO-H2-ICE-CHP-Demonstrator>

689

- <https://zenodo.org/records/17020672>

GLOSSARY

- 690
- 691 BAT
- 692 Battery.
- 693 CF
- 694 Characterization factor. A numerical factor derived from a characterization model (i.e. impact indicator) in LCA,
- 695 applied to the quantities of energy/material inputs or emission of a system, to quantify the associated impacts
- 696 with respect to a given environmental category.
- 697 DES
- 698 Decentralized energy systems. Systems that operate mostly independently from conventional grids, often in
- 699 relatively small scale and focusing on supply from clean energy sources.
- 700 EF
- 701 Environmental Footprint (in LCA). Global life-cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method recommended by the
- 702 European Union. Includes 16 environmental indicators.
- 703 GRID
- 704 Interconnected network for electricity exchange between producers to consumers, here referring to the national
- 705 German electricity grid.
- 706 GSHP
- 707 Global sensitivity analysis. Traditional or local sensitivity analysis study how the variation of one uncertain input
- 708 within a model influences the output, while keeping the others at their original values or distribution of values. A
- 709 global sensitivity analysis applies this logic to all inputs with uncertainties to compare them and study the
- 710 complete variability behavior of the model.
- 711 GSHP
- 712 Ground-source heat pump.
- 713 H₂
- 714 Dihydrogen. Commonly referred to as hydrogen outside of chemistry research for simplicity.
- 715 H₂C
- 716 Hydrogen compressor.
- 717 H₂S
- 718 Hydrogen storage.
- 719 ICE-CHP
- 720 Internal conversion engine for combined heat and power. Combined heat and power (also called cogeneration)
- 721 converts chemical energy from fuel into both electrical (el) and thermal (th) energy. In ICE, the chemical energy
- 722 of the fuel is converted through combustion, as opposed to the pure chemical conversion used in fuel cells.
- 723 LCA
- 724 Life-cycle assessment. This approach usually focus on assessing average environmental impacts of a system,
- 725 across multiple impact categories, relative to a unit of reference. The materials and emissions inventory of the
- 726 assessed system are considered throughout the complete life-cycle. This typically allows comparison of
- 727 technological alternatives for a given function, aiming to achieve sustainability.
- 728 LCI
- 729 Life-cycle inventory. Phase of inventory during an LCA, where material/energy flows and emissions of a system
- 730 are quantified relative to the functional unit used for the study.

731 LCIA
732 Life-cycle impact assessment. Phase of assessment during an LCA, where impact indicators (e.g. global
733 warming potential) are used to apply CFs to the LCI to quantify the impact of a system to an environmental
734 category (e.g. climate change).

735 L
736 Load boundary. System boundary limited to the flows directly involved in meeting the electricity and heat
737 demand of the buildings considered.

738 LE
739 Load + Excess boundary. System boundary taking into account all the flows involved in the system by adding
740 the electricity overproduction sent to the grid to flows directly involved in meeting the electricity and heat
741 demand of the buildings considered.

742 LEG
743 Load + Excess – Grid (DE) boundary. System boundary taking into account all the flows involved in the system
744 but considering the electricity overproduction sent to the grid as replacing production from the German
745 electricity grid for external users.

746 N_{std}
747 Normalized standard deviation. In the relevant sections of the article, N_{std} value corresponds to the standard
748 deviation normalized by the mean of the distribution considered.

749 PEMEL
750 Proton-exchange membrane electrolyzer.

751 PV
752 Photovoltaic.

753 TEA
754 Techno-economic analysis. This approach usually focus on assessing specific technical and economic feasibility
755 of a system, often using process simulation software to model the operational phase, which constitutes the base
756 of the assessment.

757 TES
758 Thermal energy system.

759 WT
760 Wind turbine.

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895

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897 **P. Robineau:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation,
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905 All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

906 **DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST**

907 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could
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912 **GENERATIVE AI IN SCIENTIFIC WORK**

913 After algorithmic conceptualization, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to help in the writing of the Python
914 procedures used to treat the OpenModelica simulation outputs and for data analysis and visualization of the LCA
915 results. The Python procedures were tested on minimal examples and contains validation steps. After writing the
916 original draft of this manuscript, the authors also used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to help improve readability of
917 some sections – without altering the factual content. The authors reviewed and edited the manuscript as needed
918 and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

919 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

920 All data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper or in the supplementary information
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